

Students' Online Learning Engagement Problems in the New Normal: Their Insights to Maximize Learning

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ABSTRACT

The highlight of this study ascertained the problems encountered by the SED students in the new normal as they have their online classes. The study showed how they maximize their learning engagement and what insights they have gained. Sixty-two SED College students responded to the survey questionnaire floated online via Google Form. The dominant problem the students encountered was on the internet connectivity, especially for students who lived in the remote areas. The coping strategy to address this problem was to strengthen their drive and motivation to finish their studies so they could have work in the future. Students maximize their learning engagement through “participation, engagement and attention in class.” The insights gained during the new normal encouraged the students to have optimism and motivation. The values and lessons learned during the new normal revealed that “responsibility, active participation and motivation” surfaced.

Subject Area

Learning Engagement

Keywords: *Online Learning Engagement, New Normal*

INTRODUCTION

With the advent of the pandemic COVID-19, the education system across the globe was shaken up. The adverse impact of the pandemic to education sends school authorities to divert face-to-face classes to online learning modalities. School authorities and students do not have the choice than to adjust the new way of teaching and learning process. How to cope with the new normal is a question in the academe including the students and the parents. Curriculum, classes' schedules and strategies were planned and arranged with the end to still deliver the quality education the students deserve despite the various challenges due to the pandemic.

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Online Learning (as cited in Barrot, Llenares, Rosario, 2021) refers to a learning environment that uses the internet, other technological devices and tools for synchronous and asynchronous instructional delivery and management of academic programs. Synchronous online learning involves real-time interactions between the teacher and the students, while asynchronous online learning occurs without a strict schedule for different students (Singh, & Thurman, 2019). Within the context of Covid-19 pandemic, online learning has taken the status of interim remote teaching that serves as a response to an exigency. However, migration to new learning space has faced several major concerns relating to policy, pedagogy, logistics, socioeconomic factors, technology, and psychosocial factors (Donitsa- Schmidt & Ramot, 2020).

Online learning means a lot of challenges and problems encountered by students. Besides being caught not prepared with the new set up, a number of concerns and issues were met in the context of online learning. Thus, this should be addressed to acquire learning at its maximum end. Some of these problems encountered at the start of the new normal were; students lack of motivation to engage in class since they are not used to work in isolation. Lack of face-to-face arrangements may lead to students giving up without anyone noticing it.

Student engagement, is the extent to which students show attention, curiosity, optimism and interest in the material that they are being taught. This may refer to student's cognitive investment in their learning, including participating and students' learning improvement when engagement levels are high. Moreover, they added that student engagement refers to student's willingness to participate in and be successful in their learning process. Student engagement is made up of emotional, behavioral and cognitive engagement.

During the start of the conduct of online classes, students lamented about internet connectivity, no gadget and budget for their load to be able to connect them online, thereby enable them to participate in class. This means no active modular modality for them not to spend money in answering their tasks and quizzes in class. On the part of the students there is no active participation in class. Their engagement in online classes is a problem, thereby making them demotivated to learn and participate actively in the conduct of their classes supposedly.

This current study is focused on the problems encountered by SED students on their learning engagement online, so that these students will be understood better, their success in their chosen course is ensured. Thus, this study aimed to facilitate a more improved teaching-learning process in the School of Education at San Isidro College. Moreover, this study ascertained what insights, values and lessons are gained by the students to maximize their learning online.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

This study ascertained the problems encountered by the SED students in their learning engagement online and their insights to maximize their learning. Specifically, it answered the following problems:

1. What are the problems encountered by the SED students in their learning engagement online and how do they address these problems?
2. What values/ lessons did the students learn from their online classes and how did they maximize their learning engagement?
3. What insights did the students gain from their online class experiences?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Online student engagement is particularly inflected by a sense of belonging. “Online learners, perhaps more so than face-to-face learners, need deliberately orchestrated, multiple opportunities to engage with others so that expression, development, tolerance and recognition of their diverse identities may in part compensate for any lack felt by not learning physical presence” (Delachety, Verenokina, & Jones, 2014) as cited in Farrell & Bruton (2020). Online learners may experience disengagement in class activities because of the set up. They need to learn to work in isolation where it may lead to problems of active participation among the students.

A study in 2021 by Barrot, Llenares, and del Rosario investigated about students’ online learning challenges during the pandemic and how they cope with them. Their study revealed that the online challenges of college students varied in terms of type and extent. Accordingly, their greatest challenge was linked to their learning environment at home, while their least challenge was technological literacy and competency. Given the result of this study, students were more comfortable learning inside the school campus, because it is where they used to be when they started studying since first grade. Furthermore, is the social factor where they can mingle with their peers and classmates, while learning at home is just a supplement of what has been learned inside the class or in school. This further implies that students faced a lot of problems in adjusting to the new normal. The findings of this study further revealed that the Covid-19 pandemic had the greatest impact on the quality of the learning experiences and students’ coping with the situation they were in.

An article was published online by Wiley Online Library on what works and why is there a need for engagement in online learning. It was stressed that by applying the theories and techniques for student engagement in online class, there is interest in learning. It helps higher education produce graduates who can contribute to their families, communities, and the economy. Engagement techniques could be one key to making online learning productive for the institution. More importantly, it ensures that students are successful as they pursue a college degree. Moreover, achieving student engagement may be a critical key to making online learning an essential component of higher education and indispensable part of the institution’s future.

Farrwell and Brunton (2020) conducted a study the Balancing Act: A Window into Online Student Engagement Experiences. The findings of the study indicate that successful online students’ engagement was influenced by a number of psychosocial factors such as peer community, an engaging online teacher, confidence and by structure factors such as life load and course design.

Mikaela Amadora published an article online on “Common Problems that Occur During Online Classes.” According to her, in online classes, there was never a day when a student has not voiced out complains such as “Can someone tell the professor I/he/she got disconnected?” “Oops! Where did he go? (referring to the professor who doesn’t realize he got out off),” and “I have unstable Wi-Fi.” She added that “Our country is an internet-challenged country.” This is a problem that had caused delays in implementing the remote learning in general. Because our country is an internet-challenged country, more problems may arise in this online learning specifically on the engagement of students. How can students maximize learning online with all these problems encountered in this new normal learning modality?

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted the descriptive mixed methods approach to answer the research questions. This allowed the researchers to collect data about problems encountered by SED students in their learning engagement online and their insights for maximizing learning. In categorizing the responses of the students, frequency and percentage were used. Responses were encoded and categorized into similar ideas or themes using the thematic analysis to inductively ascertain what were the problems encountered by the SED students in their learning engagement online and their insights or reflections to maximize learning. The data were gathered through interview using open-ended questions.

The study was conducted at San Isidro College, specifically in the School of Education. It has three (3) departments namely: College, Integrated Basic Education (IBED), and the Institute of Technical and Health Related Training Programs (ITHRP). The college was duly recognized by CHED and the DepED. Since its establishment, the college strives to deliver quality Catholic education; where students grow to be God-fearing, competent, disciplined, and service oriented in their chosen fields. San Isidro College was founded in 1949 and is the only Catholic higher education institution in the city. The college aimed to form men and women of prayer and for others.

The participants of the study were the 62 students officially enrolled at San Isidro College, School of Education during the Academic Year 2021-2022. There are 36 (58.1%) students from the Bachelor of Elementary Education, 5 (8.1%) from the Bachelor of Secondary Education major in English; 4 (6.5%) from the Bachelor of Secondary Education major in Filipino; 2 (3.1%) from the Bachelor of Secondary Education major in Math; and 15(24.2%) from the Bachelor of Secondary Education major in Values Education.

The research tool used in the study was the researcher-made interview guide questions that asked on the problems encountered by the SED students in their learning engagement online and their reflections/insights to maximize their learning. Interview questions were subjected to an expert's validation before conducting the interviews to gather data. Revision was done per suggestion of the expert and was piloted to five (5) students studying at San Isidro College. The items in the questions covered items related to problems encountered by the students in their learning engagement, their coping strategies, the values and lessons they learned, how students maximize learning and the insights they gained in the new normal learning modality.

The study was submitted to the School of Education for approval. After the approval, data collection was started. Given the restrictions over face-to-face interaction during the data collection period, data was collected online via the Google Form on September 1 to 30 2021.

The narrative responses were transcribed, categorized according to themes and analyzed thematically. Thematic Analysis according to Burn & Clarke (2006) as cited in Kiger & Varpio, (2020) is a method on analyzing qualitative data that entails a data set to identify, analyze, and check on report patterns. Thematic analysis is an appropriate method of analysis for seeking to understand experiences, thoughts or behaviors across a data set.

The data gathered from the statement of the problems questions were categorized into themes and analyzed using frequency and percentages. Thematic Analysis was used to analyze the

responses. This was done through identifying common themes, topics, ideas, and patterns responses of the participants. This is in reference to Kiger & Varpio (2020) which follows a six-step process; (1) familiarizing the data; (2) generating initial codes; (3) searching for themes; (4) reviewing themes; (5) defining and naming themes; and (6) producing the report.

RESULTS

This study was conducted to ascertain the problems encountered by the SED students in their learning engagement online. Thus, this study explored the problems, coping strategies, and insights to maximize their learning. Valuable information was obtained from the responses of the participants. Frequencies and percentages were employed to treat the data while their narrative responses were qualitatively analyzed.

Table 1 shows the summary responses of the SED students on the problems they encountered in their learning engagement online. Majority of the students (82.35%) indicates that their problem is on the internet connection. They have online classes that needs to have stable internet connection to be engaged in their class sessions. On the other hand, the response on “*no motivation to join*” has the lowest percentage of 14.5%.

This result is somehow aligned to the article published online by Amadora (2021) where the problem in online class is on internet connection. Accordingly, there was never a day when a student did not complain about being disconnected, or their professor experienced disconnection due to slow or no internet connection. As an internet-challenged country the intermittent connectivity caused delays in implementing effective learning and sustaining students’ engagement in their classes to ensure learning.

Table 1. Summary Responses of the SED students on the Problems Encountered in their Learning Engagement Online

Problems Encountered	<i>f</i>	%
No internet connection	51	82.3
Too many requirements	23	37.1
Boring	13	21
No clear instruction	13	21
No motivation to join	9	14.5
Overthinking/ Feeling of Anxiety	1	1.6
Unstable internet connection	1	1.6
Less learning	1	1.6
Technical Problem	1	1.6
Low quality of gadgets and no proper Learning environment	1	1.6

Table 2 reflects the coping strategies of the students to address their problems in the New Normal. The total responses were categorized into 11 themes or ideas. The highest number out of the total responses of the students was on “*Drive and motivation to finish studying; work to accomplish what is required*” with 19 (30.65%) students who responded on this theme. Some of the students’ responses were: “*By being motivated to Learn;*” “*Motivate yourself and embrace the new learning context*”; and “*I engaged myself to motivate and encourage specially in our situation today.*”

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Table 2. Coping Strategies of the students to address their Problems in the New Normal.

Themes on the coping strategies	Respondents	f	%
Drive and motivation to finish studying; work to accomplish what is required	1, 19, 12, 25, 26, 29, 32, 33, 35, 38, 39, 42, 46, 48, 51, 52, 54, 10, 17	19	30.65
Avoiding distractions; more focused	4, 18, 21, 44, 49, 50, 53, 62, 11	9	14.52
Always prepare; advanced study; check emails and assignments	2, 8, 34, 41, 56, 61	6	9.68
Search for sources to engage online; Borrow gadgets	7, 45, 85	3	4.84
Collaboration and communication	13, 43	2	3.23
Participation, involvement and engagement during class	16, 5, 3, 24, 27, 40, 55, 59	10	16.13
Time management	22, 47, 60	3	4.84
Adjust and adapt to the new normal; Have a positive mindset	9, 28, 36, 57	4	6.45
Reach out to professors	15, 20	2	3.23
Futuristic outlook	30	1	1.60
Enough funds for internet Connection	37	1	1.60
Others	23, 31	2	3.23
Total		62	100

The result implies that despite the number of problems encountered by students, they need to cope-up to acquire learning. They are motivated to learn and finish what has been started amidst the pandemic and amidst the new normal learning modality.

Moreover, despite the fact that online learning is a drastic change in the delivery of lessons to students, they still find ways to acquire learning. It can be gleaned from the result that majority of the respondents (30.65%) keep themselves motivated to learn, to finish their studies and to accomplish according to what is required of them as online learners. According to them, they have to “*keep themselves motivated to learn new knowledge.*” The least strategy they used was on having “*a futuristic outlook and enough funds for internet connection*”.

According to Amadora (2020), one of the common problems encountered during online is short attention span. This problem remains universal. She added that with online class, it takes a strong will-power to stay awake and focused. Although it is new learning modality, students keep themselves motivated to learn to finish their degree.

Table 3 reflects the summary of responses on the values and lessons learned by the students during the new normal. These responses are categorized into similar themes. It can be gleaned from the result that there are seven (7) themes which came out from the responses of the students.

Majority of respondents indicate that they learned the values of being responsible to actively participate in class, and be motivated to ensure success in learning despite this online learning delivery. Their responses include: “I learn that you must be motivated and set priorities in life before anything else especially in terms of our education.” Moreover, the result implies that students learned their lessons and acquire values from their experiences during the new normal. Motivation plays a big role in the students' learning. They have to be motivated in order to finish their studies. With the COVID-19 pandemic, students have to embrace the new normal. They

have to keep themselves motivated despite the slow internet connection, the kind of gadget they used for online class, and other issues they met in this new normal.

Table 3. Values and lessons learned during the New Normal

Themes	Respondents	<i>f</i>	%
Motivation to learn	5, 11, 21	3	4.83
Stay positive, Stay focused	57, 61, 50, 54, 7, 4, 41, 51, 59	9	14.52
Have Patience	43, 55, 48, 58, 34, 30, 33, 9, 12, 25, 29, 22	12	19.35
Time Management	52, 47, 32, 6, 18, 39, 38	7	11.29
Responsibility, Active Participation, Motivation	1, 2, 10, 14, 16, 23, 53, 56, 24, 27, 35, 11, 21	12	24.18
Value teachers/ things, Self-Discipline	8, 28, 40, 44, 42	5	8.10
Independence	46, 20, 31, 26	5	6.45
Others	36, 45, 3, 15, 19, 49, 60, 62, 48, 17,13	11	16.12
Total		62	100

Table 4 presents how students maximize their learning in this new normal. Their responses were categorized into five similar themes. It can be gleaned from the table that 26 SED students claimed they maximized their learning in this new normal through “participating actively in class, to be engaged in class, and be attentive.” This theme got the highest percentage of 41.9%. The students express their ideas like: “As a student, I can maximize my learning during this time of pandemic by engaging myself in every subject who conducted online classes.” “I participate in class, to share ideas, and opinions”. “For me to be able to speak in class, I will study the lesson in advance, that my instructors have given in the Google classroom.” Evidently, from the responses of the students, despite the new normal they still manage to participate actively in class, keep themselves engaged and be attentive on what their instructors taught.

Table 4. Summary of responses on how students maximize their learning is this new normal

Themes	Respondents	<i>f</i>	%
Participation; Engagement; Attention	46, 50, 54, 1, 5, 7, 9, 33, 13, 17, 4, 25, 39, 27, 29, 8, 12, 14, 16, 22, 24, 45, 47, 36, 58	26	41.9
Time Management	15, 23, 3, 28, 30, 37, 49, 55, 52	9	14.52
Collaboration/ Connection	19, 26, 32, 34, 38	5	8.10
Motivation	2, 10, 20, 31, 51, 35, 42, 44, 47, 59, 60	11	17.7
Independence	18, 41, 43, 56, 62	5	8.10
Others	40, 53, 57, 11, 61, 21	6	9.68
Total		62	100

Table 5 presents the summary of the responses of the SED students on the insights they gained in this new normal. The responses were categorized into four similar themes. The dominant insight of students was on “being optimistic and being motivated to learn.” This allowed the students to realize that they need to be motivated to ensure success on their end.

Table 5. Insight gained by the students in this new normal

Themes of Relevant Topics	Respondents	f	%
Collaboration	3, 41, 42	3	4.84
Participation, Accountability Engagement	31, 33, 55, 50, 52, 54, 4, 5, 8, 12, 47, 21, 6, 27, 16, 38	16	25.81
Optimism, Motivation	57, 50, 56, 58, 59, 60, 9, 11, 13, 22, 28, 40, 62, 10, 17, 19, 25, 24, 35, 46, 37, 39, 30, 32, 34	25	40.32
Time Management, Disciplined	23, 18, 26, 45, 51, 53, 2, 28	8	12.9
Others	15, 43, 24, 30, 1, 29, 36, 44, 49, 61	10	16.13
Total		62	100

One student stated that “*During this time of pandemic, it is very important for us to be inspired, not only by ourselves but with our classes*”. The students believe that there is a future waiting for them. They could benefit meaningful leaning when they participate and engage in the discussion and class activities facilitated by their teachers

Meanwhile, the insight on *collaboration* got the least percentage with 3 or 4.84% respondents. Evidently from the responses of students on their insights in the new normal they viewed optimism and motivation could help them cope with the new modality of delivering education.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study ascertained the problems encountered by the SED students in their learning engagement online and what insights they gained in maximizing learning this new normal. Findings revealed that the majority (82.3%) of the students have no internet connection. Internet connectivity is a problem for students especially for those students living in remote places. The coping strategy to address this problem was to strengthen their drive and motivation to finish their studies so they could have work in the future.

When students were asked on how they maximize their learning in this new normal, 41.9% of the respondents answered on “participation, engagement and attention in class.” Despite the new normal they “strive to participate to engage and to be attentive in class.” The insights they gained during the new normal encouraged the students to have optimism and motivation. Furthermore, they learned during the new normal, “responsibility, active participation and motivation” were so important during this new normal.

The overall findings indicate that the students’ answer vary from one student to another. Nonetheless students employed strategies like keeping themselves motivated to finish their studies and to actively participate in class. However, the strategies that students adopted during this new normal may have been shaped by different factors like availability of resources, students’ personality, family structure, relationship with peers and teachers.

The SED students at San Isidro College encountered problems in their online learning engagement, and they viewed these as the outcome of the pandemic, where both teachers and the students are not prepared. The findings of this study provided insights with the important themes related to online student engagement. These are valuable information for further research practice.

For the School of Education supporting teaching, learning, and designing online classes, should be cognizant of the students' problems that affect their learning engagement. This study can be expanded to see results on the problems encountered from various perspectives. One could explore on how and why different themes emerged from the students' responses. Future research could examine the causes of students' challenges and problems in their online learning engagement.

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